

HbA1c level in iron deficiency anemia in non-diabetics – A case control studyAakash Dubey^{1*}, Anita Arya², Rita Singh Saxena³, Simmi Dube⁴¹Post-graduate Resident, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India²Professor, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India³Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India⁴Professor and Head, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The study was conducted to study the HbA1c levels in cases of iron deficiency anemia and compare with controls as well as to HbA1c level in mild, moderate, and severe iron deficiency anemia.**Methodology:** This was a case control observational study on non-diabetic subjects diagnosed with iron deficiency anemia presenting at Department of Medicine, Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal during the study period of June 2022 to January 2024. Age and sex matched nondiabetic controls without iron deficiency anemia were selected in control group. Medical History was obtained, and examination was done. A record of baseline investigation was made, and clinical parameters were documented.**Results:** This study was conducted on a total of 82 cases with iron deficiency anemia and 82 age and sex matched controls. Mean HbA1C level was higher in Cases (5.50) compared to Controls (4.99) ($p < 0.05$). We found that severity of anemia also correlated with increased HbA1c level ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). Patients with higher HbA1c levels (5.7 – 6.0) have low serum ferritin (5.72 ± 1.24) and low Hb levels (5.9 ± 0.3) ($p < 0.05$).**Conclusions:** According to the finding of study those with IDA had higher HbA1c compared to controls that were non anemic. It was also found in the study that as severity of anemia increases, the level of HbA1c also increase. Increased HbA1c level IDA may be due to change in quaternary structure of Hb or due to relatively decreased HbA1c levels in anemics. These findings underscore the importance of diagnosis of IDA to prevent over diagnosis of diabetes and pre-diabetics.**Keywords:** Glycemia Level, Iron Deficiency Anemia, Association, Ferritin, Non-Diabetes, Case Control.**Clinical Significance:** Iron deficiency anemia is a key factor that affects HbA1c level and IDA must be corrected before making a diagnosis or initiating therapy for diabetes on the basis of HbA1c. So, IDA should be kept in mind before making diagnosis on the basis of HbA1c and this will also increase the reliability in diagnosis diabetes.

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Introduction

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is a prevalent global health concern, affecting individuals across diverse demographics. While the primary consequence of IDA is the impairment of oxygen transport due to decreased hemoglobin levels, recent studies have indicated a potential association between iron deficiency anemia and altered glycemic regulation in non-diabetic individuals.[1] Diabetes mellitus (DM), a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by impaired insulin function or production, has been extensively studied for its impact on various physiological processes.[2] However, the intricate interplay between iron metabolism, hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels, and glycemic control in non-diabetics with IDA remains an understudied area. Glycated hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) is a critical component of hemoglobin, constituting approxi-

mately 5% of total hemoglobin in non-diabetic individuals.[3] Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) is a pivotal marker in assessing long-term glycemic control, reflecting the average blood glucose levels over the preceding 2-3 months.[4] While its utility is widely recognized in managing diabetes, recent investigations have unveiled potential alterations in HbA1c levels among individuals with iron deficiency anemia, irrespective of diabetic status.[5] This intriguing finding raises questions about the complex interactions between iron metabolism, erythropoiesis, and glycemic control in individuals without diabetes. A comprehensive exploration of HbA1c levels in non-diabetics with iron deficiency anemia is essential to unravel the underlying mechanisms and establish the clinical implications of this association.[6]

Iron deficiency anemia, a prevalent form of nutritional deficiency worldwide and particularly common in India, has been associated with alterations in HbA1c levels according to various studies.[7] Conflicting findings in existing research prompted a closer examination of the effects of Iron deficiency anemia on HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals, particularly within the Indian population. few have shown an increase in HbA1c levels among individuals with iron deficiency anemia while other show no significant difference. Some researchers, like Guo et al,[8] demonstrated higher HbA1c levels in these patients, which significantly decreased with iron treatment. Conversely, other studies, such as those conducted by Sinha et al,[9] reported an increase in HbA1c levels with iron deficiency anemia treatment. Given this conflicting landscape, our study aimed to elucidate whether HbA1c levels are elevated in non-diabetic adults with iron deficiency anemia in the Indian population. Understanding this association is critical for accurate diagnostic interpretations and underscores the importance of addressing iron deficiency before making significant clinical decisions based on increased HbA1c levels alone. This study aims to bridge the existing knowledge gap by delving into the intricate relationship between iron deficiency anemia and HbA1c levels in non-diabetic individuals. Understanding the nuances of this association has the potential to redefine our approach to anemia management and shed light on novel factors influencing glycemic control. Through an in-depth analysis of clinical data and laboratory parameters, this research endeavors to contribute valuable insights that may pave the way for targeted interventions and personalized healthcare strategies for individuals affected by iron deficiency anemia in the absence of diabetes. The objectives of our study were to observe the HbA1c levels in cases of iron deficiency anemia as compared with controls as well as to correlated HbA1c level with severity of iron deficiency anemia.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted as a case control observational study on non-diabetic patients diagnose with iron deficiency anemia presenting at Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College and associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal during the study period of June 2022 to January 2024. All the

non-diabetic cases (FBS <110 mg/dl, RBS <200 mg/dl and HbA1c <6.4%) with anemia (Hb <13 mg/dl in males and <12 mg/dl in females), belonging to more than 14 years of age with microcytic hypochromic blood picture and low serum ferritin (<100 mcg/ml in females and <200 mcg/ml in males) were included whereas pregnant women, patients with microcytic hypochromic blood picture due to other cause (thalassemia .) and patients with other chronic disease(kidney failure, liver failure, heart failure infection etc.) were excluded from the study.

After obtaining clearance from Institute's ethical committee, non-diabetic patients with iron deficiency were selected as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Age and sex matched controls without iron deficiency anemia were selected in control group. Medical History was obtained, and examination was done. History of comorbidities like hyper/hypothyroidism, hypertension was noted. A record of baseline investigation was made, and clinical parameters were documented.

Patients were classified according to the severity of anemia as

- Mild Anemia- 11-13 gm/dL
- Moderate Anemia - 7-10.9 gm/dL
- Severe Anemia <7 gm/dL

HbA1c levels were compared between the groups and within the group with varying severity of anemia.

Statistical Analysis

Data was compiled using MS Excel and analyzed using IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software version 21 (IBM corporation: NY, USA). Categorical and continuous variables were represented as frequency and mean (standard deviation) respectively. Chi square test and unpaired t test were applied to find association and P value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Observation & Results

This study was conducted on a total of 82 cases with IDA and 82 age and sex matched controls.

Table 1: Comparison of baseline variables between cases and controls

Baseline variables	Cases (n=82)		Controls (n=82)		P value	
	n	%	n	%		
Age (years)	16-20	15	18.9	16	0.68	
	21-30	20	24.4	16		
	31-40	17	20.7	16		
	41-60	30	36.5	30		
	61-70	0	0	4		4.9
Gender	Females	32	39	32	39	NA

	Males	50	61	50	61	
Clinical findings	Fatigue	74	90.2	73	89	0.89
	Dyspnea	55	67.1	55	67.1	NA
	Glossitis	36	43.9	7	8.5	0.001*
	Nail changes	27	32.9	2	2.4	0.001*

The mean age of cases was 35.35±13.3 years whereas that of controls was 36.42±14.84 years. Cases and controls were comparable with respect to

age and sex (p>0.05), however, glossitis and nail changes were observed in significantly higher proportions of cases as compared to controls (p<0.05).

Table 2: Comparison of the mean RBS and HbA1c between the groups

RBS and HbA1c		Cases	Controls	P value
RBS	Mean	133.57	134.71	0.74
	SD	22.24	22.78	
	Range	100-191	100-188	
HbA1c	Mean	5.47	4.99	0.001*
	SD	0.268	0.127	
	Range	5-5.9	4.8-5.2	

Table 2 shows similar Random Blood Sugar (RBS) levels in both the groups, with Cases at 133.57 and Controls at 134.71 and is not significant. But mean HbA1C levels were higher in Cases (5.474) com-

pared to Controls (4.991) with p value (0.001) which suggest significant difference between cases and controls.

Figure 1: Distribution according to severity of anemia in cases

Out of a total of 82 participants, 31.7% (26 individuals) were classified as having mild anemia, while the majority, 43.9% (36 individuals), exhibit-

ed moderate anemia. A smaller portion, 24.4% (20 individuals), was identified with severe anemia (Figure 1).

Table 3: Distribution of mean HbA1c based on severity of anemia

Severity of Anemia	N	Minimum (HbA1c)	Maximum (HbA1c)	Mean (HbA1c)	S.D	P – value
Mild	26	5.25	5.6	5.204	0.1183	0.001*
Moderate	36	5.51	5.6	5.514	0.0833	
Severe	20	5.81	5.9	5.805	0.1146	

We found a statistically significant relationship between the severity of anemia and HbA1c levels,

suggesting that higher anemia severity is associated with increased HbA1c level (p<0.05) (Table 3).

Table 4: Correlation of HbA1c with ferritin, TIBC and mean hemoglobin in cases

HbA1c	N	Serum Ferritin (Mean±S.D.)	TIBC (Mean±S.D.)	Hb (Mean±S.D.)
4.7 – 5.6	62	16.29±5.29	481±38	9.827±1.37
5.7 – 6.0	20	510.55±5.59	512±15.84	5.52±0.83
P value		0.01*	0.55	0.01*

Table 4 suggests patients with HbA1c levels of 4.7 – 5.6% have higher ferritin levels (16.24 ± 5.29) and higher Hb levels (9.827 ± 1.3) while patients with higher HbA1c levels (5.7 – 6.0) have low serum ferritin (10.55 ± 5.59) and low Hb levels (5.52 ± 0.83) ($p < 0.05$).

Discussions

We aimed to study the relationship between iron deficiency anemia and glycated hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels in non-diabetic Indian adolescents and adults, particularly given the increasing prevalence of both conditions in the population. Conducted as a case-control study at the Department of Medicine in GMC Bhopal, this research encompasses 82 cases and 82 controls, aiming to elucidate the impact of iron deficiency anemia on HbA1c levels. Understanding this relationship is paramount, as HbA1c is a key marker for long-term glucose control and diabetes management. This study underscores the importance of rigorous diabetes control in patients with iron deficiency anemia, which may have significant implications for clinical practice and patient outcomes in the Indian context.

The study found higher HbA1c levels in Cases compared to Controls. This aligns with findings from other research indicating that IDA is associated with elevated HbA1c levels in non-diabetic patients. For instance, a study reported mean HbA1c levels of 6.11% in IDA patients compared to 5.01% in controls, demonstrating a significant difference that supports the current study's result. [1] Coban et al [10] in their study found that mean HbA1c level of iron deficient Anemia patients was 7.4 ± 0.8 while that in healthy subjects was 5.9 ± 0.5 with p value < 0.001 which was highly significant. Shanthi et al [11] found mean HbA1c level 7.6 ± 0.5 in iron deficient Anemia patients who were non-diabetic while mean HbA1c level in non-Anemia nondiabetic subjects was 5.5 ± 0.8 with p value < 0.001 which is statistically significant.

Our study noted a significant relationship between HbA1c levels and lower serum ferritin and Hemoglobin levels. This is consistent with findings from study done by Bindayel et al [12] that have shown that lower iron stores are linked to increased HbA1c levels, suggesting a biochemical interplay between iron status and glycemic control. Sinha et

al [9] documented that the mean Hemoglobin and mean serum ferritin levels increased in anemia patients over 2 months of iron treatment.

The distribution of anemia severity in Cases (43.9% moderate, 31.7% mild, 24.4% severe) reflects findings from other studies that categorise anemia severity similarly. The association between higher HbA1c levels and more severe anemia has also been documented by Mehrotra, et al. [13] indicating that as anemia worsens, HbA1c rises.

The current study's findings on HbA1c levels in non-diabetics with iron deficiency anemia are largely supported by existing literature, which confirms the significant impact of IDA on Hemoglobin levels and glycemic control. The consistent patterns across demographic, clinical, and biochemical parameters emphasise the importance of considering iron status when interpreting HbA1c levels in non-diabetic populations. Further research is warranted to elucidate the mechanisms underlying these associations and to determine the clinical implications for managing patients with iron deficiency anemia with high hba1c. Also effect of IDA on HbA1c in diabetics needs to be studied. The sample size may not be large enough to detect subtle differences in some parameters, limiting the generalizability of the findings. The cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to infer causality between anemia and the observed clinical and biochemical parameters. The study population may not be representative of the broader population, as it might be limited to a specific geographic region or demographic group, affecting the applicability of the results to other populations. The study may not account for all potential confounding factors that could influence the prevalence of anemia and its related parameters, such as nutritional status, comorbid conditions, and medication use.

Conclusions

In the current study the influence of iron deficiency anemia on HbA1c level was studied. According to the finding of study those with IDA had higher HbA1c compared to controls that were non anemic. It was also found in the study that as severity of anemia increases, the level of HbA1c also increase. Increased HbA1c level IDA may be due to change in quaternary structure of Hb. These findings underscore the importance of diagnosis of IDA to prevent over diagnosis of diabetes and pre-diabetics.

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